

Perceived and Actual AI Deepfakes: The Case of Sudan

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About the Author: Eilaf Mohamed is a computer science student and aspiring digital governance and AI safety researcher with a background in policy advocacy, STEM education, and entrepreneurship. As part of her fellowship with AMEL, she is researching the impacts of technology on Sudanese society and the potential of technology in advancing democracy in Sudan.

Executive Summary

Sudan's AI deepfake risk currently appears driven more by demand-side vulnerabilities than the volume of AI deepfake content. While AI-generated disinformation in Sudanese feeds remains limited¹, perceived (alleged) AI deepfakes and general AI skepticism worsen the situation and contribute to general uncertainty in multimedia content. Within the analyzed cases, we found that the prominent stance was distrust driven more by motivated reasoning and contextual reliance than by durable AI detection skills. In practice rejection or acceptance to AI deepfake often reflects belief-driven judgement more than technical assesment². These weak defenses leave the information environment vulnerable to future sophisticated AI deepfake campaigns and risk normalizing truth indifference. Short-term interventions should prioritize modality-agnostic demand-side interventions such as pre-bunking, AI literacy, scaled fact-checks, and tiplines that strengthen public resilience across all forms of disinformation. More technical AI-specific and supply-side interventions can be developed as institutional capacity and technology allow.

Contextual Background

Deepfake is the process of creating fake digital content or using deep learning techniques to manipulate authentic materials; the content consists of text, audio, images, or video (Gambín et al., 2024). A central concern in the literature on the societal impacts of deepfakes is the use of synthetic media in disinformation campaigns, as visual and auditory communication establishes fluency due to the sense of familiarity it gives to the viewers; therefore, the content is perceived to be more truthful (Helmus, 2022; Vaccari & Chadwick, 2020). AI deepfake poses security and political risks because abundant public footage of politicians lets malicious actors easily create high-quality deepfakes for manipulating elections, escalating ethnic divides (Helmus, 2022; Schwartz, 2018; Vaccari & Chadwick, 2020), and reducing trust in institutions (Helmus, 2022). In conflict settings, AI deepfakes

¹ This statement holds as of the time of writing this paper.

² These findings should be interpreted with caution given the limitations of inferring beliefs from social media comments. Refer to Annex B.

can be used to legitimize war and uprisings, falsify orders, sow confusion, divide ranks, undermine popular support, polarize societies, divide allies, and discredit leaders (Byman et al., 2023).

Epistemic Effects: Uncertainty and Erosion of Trust

One of the societal impacts of AI deepfakes is increasing uncertainty and undermining trustworthy sources of information (Helmus, 2022; Vaccari & Chadwick, 2020). This confirms Schwartz's (2018) theory that "the greatest threat is not that people will be deceived, but that they will come to regard everything as deception," which some scholars call an epistemological threat. Their theory builds on Downs' (1957) theory that uncertainty is created because of the high cost of accessing information; therefore, deepfakes increase that cost, and truth becomes a matter of indifference (Vaccari & Chadwick, 2020). Building on this discussion of uncertainty, Liu et al. (2025) introduce a new dimension to reality apathy, or truth indifference, which is AI self-efficacy, and they found that low AI self-efficacy resulted in higher cynicism. Put differently, truth becomes indifferent, not just as a passive response to misinformation, but also because the users perceive themselves as unable to verify it.

Adding to the complexity of the problem, perceived or alleged AI deepfakes go beyond technical manipulation; while deepfakes promote belief in a falsified truth, perceived deepfakes cultivate a general AI deepfake skepticism to reject genuine truth. In that sense, deepfakes can impact objective truth when people refuse unfavorable correct information by assuming that it might be deepfakes, based on what scholars refer to as the liar's dividend (Helmus, 2022a; Schiff et al., 2024).

The models of disinformation help understand the impact of AI deepfakes and develop targeted interventions. The passive aggregator view, "Disinformed by others," suggests that the public passively absorb disinformation from malicious actors, which requires interventions to focus on the supply side, whereas the motivated public view, "Misinformed by themselves," calls for demand-side interventions and argues that, instead of disinformation shaping beliefs, disinformation is shaped by motivated reasoning (Kahan, 2017b), cognitive abilities (Pennycook & Rand, 2018; Ahmed, 2021), AI self-efficacy (Liu et al., 2025), and

other individual-level factors that increase the acceptability of disinformation. Within the demand side, two explanatory perspectives contrast: motivated reasoning and cognitive abilities. The cognitive abilities account found that people were more likely to believe in fake news³ because of low Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT) scores, regardless of political ideology (Pennycook and Rand, 2018b), whereas the motivated reasoning shows that partisan or political identity influences cognition, memory, genuine evaluation, and perceptions (Van Bavel & Pereira, 2018). While both perspectives offer valuable insights, this paper aligns more closely with the motivated reasoning perspective⁴ while also acknowledging the cognitive effort impact.

Despite global concern over AI deepfakes and AI's societal impact in general, limited research investigates the public reaction to adversarial AI deepfakes in the context of fragile states, a high-stakes context with limited trust in institutions, limited AI literacy, and escalated virtual propaganda. This study aims to understand the impact of AI deepfakes on uncertainty and trust in Sudan and explore feasible mitigation strategies through desk review, sentiment analysis of selected social media posts, and interviews with Sudanese civic tech practitioners and fact-checking organizations.

Documented AI deepfake Incidents in Sudan

The information environment in Sudan makes a perfect incubator for AI deepfakes, where the information environment has been seen by successive authoritarian regimes as a dangerous tool that enables mobilization for protesters, and therefore, the legal infrastructure is weak and designed to suppress freedom of speech and enable harmful acts against the opposition (Knight & Alsedeg, 2023). Although there exists legal infrastructure, such as the Access to Information 2015 law, which grants citizens the right to access information, but it has vague language; therefore, it protects the interests of those in power and amplifies the effect of information poverty (Knight & Alsedeg, 2023, [2]).

In Sudan, deepfakes have already been used to support the narratives of conflicting parties and mislead public opinion. While most of the disinformation supply in Sudan was either

³ The study was conducted on textual fake news.

⁴Because it was straightforward to observe within the context of this study.

textual fake news or out-of-context disinformation where real footage was taken from different contexts to mislead the public, there were some instances where AI was used to escalate virtual propaganda through voice cloning and AI deepfake technologies. The earliest one was in October 2023, when a TikTok account posted fake voice cloning recordings for Omer Al-Bashir—the ex-president—criticizing current military leaders (Goodman & Hashim, 2023)⁵. Another attempt followed in March 2024, when a voice cloning featuring Commander Abdel Fattah al-Burhan and Abdeen al-Shami discussing plans to kill civilians circulated through the X platform (Beam Reports, 2025a). Notably, the public also participated in AI deepfake generation, either for sarcasm or to raise awareness. A March 2024 public-created recording featuring the Rapid Support Commander (RSF), Hemedti, with leaders of the Forces for Freedom and Change (FFC), revealed their conspiracy before April 2023 and circulated through the X platform (Beam Reports, 2025a). Although the footage was declared to be AI-generated, it was later shared as an authentic recording, and the National TV also contributed to promoting this propaganda by sharing the AI-generated media (Beam Reports, 2025a; [1]⁶). Some of these examples are discussed in detail in the results section. The normalization of synthetic media in official communication is exemplified by the [AI-generated video](#) of Jebel Marra that has been circulated through the Sovereign Council’s official social media platforms [1].

In Sudan, AI deepfake skepticism, or perceived AI deepfakes, is a prominent problem. It occurs when footage is dismissed as AI deepfakes either by politicians to support their agendas or by the public to support their biases. The manipulation of belief by dismissing real content as deepfake can be illustrated by the classic instance of the liar dividend in June 2023, when a recording of a conversation between Mubark Ardol and other political figures was leaked. They responded by claiming that it was an AI deepfake and generated by their rivalry (Suliman, 2024).

⁵ Following the BBC investigation, TikTok removed the account.

⁶ Bracketed numbers in the text refer to personal interviews, which are detailed in Annex A.

Perceived AI deepfake Case Spotlight: Hmedti's Death

The most prominent instance of AI skepticism in the case of Sudan is Hmedti's⁷ death propaganda⁸. During the early days of the conflict, Sudanese Army Forces (SAF) supporters campaigned that Hmedti was dead, claiming that all evidence of his life was fake and AI-generated, leading the public to believe in his death, despite deepfake detection rejecting this claim (Suliman, 2024; [2]). While there have been many narratives (e.g., alternative character, Hmedti's twin), humanoid robots and AI-generated footage were among the notable ones. This incident has been influential on the public perception of AI deepfakery, especially since notable politicians have confirmed it. In their investigation of the psychological impact of Hmedti's death disinformation, Beam Reports (2025b) found that 33.1% (n=557) felt happy after hearing Hmedti's death news. They also found that among those who have seen a video of him afterwards (n=378), 52.6% believed the video was real, and the remaining 47.4% either distrusted the video or were uncertain about it. Whether the propaganda's circulation is attributed to the supply-side motives or the demand-side vulnerabilities, namely the public's motivated reasoning and limited AI literacy, the results highlight the trend of using AI to reject dislikable truth [1]. This implies that in the case of Sudan, the epistemic threat appeared to be driven by perceived deepfakes.

Building on this contextual background, we analyze two cases that included either deepfakes or perceived deepfakes from March 2023 until March 2024. We then situate our findings within the disinformation literature and insights from our personal interviews before offering recommendations to address AI deepfakes in Sudan.

⁷ Leader of Rapid Support Forces (RSF).

⁸ The impact of this propaganda was cumulative, making it difficult to identify a single most impactful tweet for analysis as the public views shifted over time.

Results

Actual Deepfake: John’s tweet

On March 15th, 2024, John Gould, an Israeli news presenter, shared a [tweet](#) with a voice recording of what he alleged to be a conversation between al-Burhan and his Deputy Chief of Operations. He accused Gen. al-Burhan of orchestrating an attack on civilians and ordering soldiers to occupy their homes. The caption described Gen. al-Burhan as the head of the Muslim Brotherhood in Sudan. He ended the caption by criticizing the global response, attributing their inaction to Israel’s non-involvement. Investigations by Beam Mersad found the recording to be AI-generated (Beam Reports, 2025a).

Our analysis of the most liked comments (n=107) revealed the following:

While the majority (82.1%) distrusted the tweet, 9.4% of the commenters trusted it, indicating limited but not negligible deception.

Figure 1

Uncertainty Distribution of the Comments on John’s Tweet

Table 1 below presents the recurring themes⁹, particularly for those who cited distrust. We found that the majority of the themes (36.6%) were related to the source's reputation and

⁹ For more details on the coding framework, refer to Annex C.

speculating on conspiracy and corrupted intent. The most interesting theme was “Believe the media but disagree with the context/narrative,” a theme in which commenters perceived the media to be truthful but attempted to contextualize it by responding to the caption. This was frequently linked to their analysis of facts or at least their perception of it, which in many cases correlated to their support for the subject of the recording. The AI usage theme appeared in only 10.3% of the comments, highlighting that truth judgement was largely influenced by source cues and motivated reasoning rather than the detection skills of the technical deepfakery of the footage. Table 1 shows the themes, their distribution, and representative quotes from the dataset.

Table 1
Qualitative Themes in the Comments on John’s Tweet

Theme	Percentage	Quote
Source distrust	36.6%	“You and your fellow Jewish media friends support the crimes of the RSF”
Believe the media but disagree with the context/narrative	19.3%	“All the buildings alburhan said located around military sites and definitely RSF militia will bomb them first, so it's better to be used by army.”
Critical analysis/fact inconsistency	16.6%	“Abdul Fattah Al Burhan isn’t the head of Muslim brotherhood”
Support for the subject of the recording	15.2%	“We fully support our Sudanese military”
AI usage	10.3%	“It's obviously fake”
other	2.1%	

Due to the lack of baseline, we performed a chi-square test of independence¹⁰ on the

¹⁰ The test excluded the "irrelevant" category and compared only evaluative comments—"trusting," "distrusting," "indifferent," and "uncertain" comments—across sources

uncertainty expression in two tweets by Salah Manaa mobilizing the same narrative: one [tweet](#) capturing real footage and the [tweet](#) in which he shared the same AI-generated recording of al-Burhan first shared by John. While we did not find a statistical significance between the uncertainty distribution on the two tweets¹¹, we are cautious in overinterpreting this result, as the “Distrusting” label in our coding scheme¹² captured both distrust in the footage and broader narrative distrust. For this reason, we placed more emphasis on qualitative theme analysis for comments on AI deepfake tweets.

Perceived AI deepfake: Ardol’s tweet

On July 16, 2023, Mubarak Ardol, a Sudanese politician, [posted](#) what he called a “Joint Public Statement” between him and Nour Al-Daem Taha. He posted this statement in response to a circulated recording on social media of them with Abdelwahab Jameel, in which they shared problematic views on their position toward the 2018 revolution and notable political leaders. In his tweet he stated that the footage was AI-generated. He argued that the public accessibility of their voice samples and the advancement of artificial intelligence technologies enabled the oppositional rallying to produce this AI deepfake footage. He also made an implicit inference to Hmedti’s death, saying, “It is now easy to imitate anyone’s voice, even those who are deceased,” as evidence for the usage of AI deepfakes in manipulating public opinion. Evidence from Suliman (2024) and the public investigations on the footage proved that the recording was authentic.

Figure 2 (n=105) shows that while 91.4% distrusted the tweet, 2.9% cited uncertainty, which is larger than the cited uncertainty in John’s tweet. The smallest proportion (1.9%) trusted the tweet and believed in AI usage, lower than in John’s tweet. This implies that those who were deceived by the perceived/alleged deepfake were relatively fewer than those deceived by actual deepfakes.

The qualitative analysis showed that the majority rejected AI usage, believing the recording was too sophisticated to be AI-generated, with insider jokes, local jargon, and voice inference, which they believed was beyond AI generative capabilities at the time, possibly

¹¹ ($\chi^2(3) = 1.29, p = .731$)

¹² Refer to Annex C for more details on the coding scheme.

reflecting some level of AI literacy skills¹³. Recurring themes included “Call for accountability” and “Source distrust,” in which people referred to his negative reputation to make judgments about the truthfulness of his claims. Additional themes included speculating on fact consistency or speculating on his prominence. These themes suggest that the narrative support and public controversy may influence the uncertainty distribution of the perceived AI deepfake.

Figure 2

Uncertainty Distribution of the Comments on Ardol’s Tweet

Our results in Table 2 show that the public were generally more distrusting toward both the actual and perceived deepfakes, with lower trust and higher uncertainty in the perceived deepfake (Ardol’s tweet) compared to the actual deepfake (John’s tweet). Contrary to Vaccari & Chadwick (2020), more distrust was cited than uncertainty¹⁴. The qualitative themes highlight that while people generally distrust AI deepfake tweets, there are many cited reasons for distrust; AI detection or the authenticity of the media is only one of them, and it is more recurring in the case of perceived/alleged deepfakes than in actual deepfakes.

¹³ Comments might not accurately reflect AI literacy. Refer to Annex B.

¹⁴ We attribute this to the difficulty of operationalizing uncertainty in comments.

Prominent factors include the alignment of the narrative accompanying the footage with the user's political views as well as the source's reputation.

Table 2

Qualitative Themes in the Comments on Ardol's Tweet

Theme	Percentage	Quote	Translated Quote
disbelieve AI usage	35.2%	عشان تعمل حوار بين ثلاثة أنفار (وفي الخلفيه جي بي أس) الثانيه كم واربعين وبرضوا بعد دقيقه وكم خمسين بوضح صوتين متداخلين بصورة يصعب علي الذكاء الاصطناعي في هذه المرحلة القيام بها	creating a conversation between three individuals (with GPS in the background) that lasts for about forty-something seconds, and then—after a minute and fifty-something—two overlapping voices appear in a way that AI, at its current stage, finds difficult to replicate.
Call for Accountability	23.4%	لمن تقول كلام ابقى قدره	If you say something, be able to stand by it.
Source distrust	16.4%	البيك معروفه من زمان يعني مابقت على التسجيل	Your true nature has been known for a long time, so it's not just about the recording
Other	8.6%		
Critical analysis/fact inconsistency	7.0%	نفس كلامك ده قلتو وقت ده هتف و اتهمته قحت وره الكلام و بعد الحرب قلت قحت مع الجنجويد و اسي نفس الشئ بتعملو	You said the same thing back then when you cheered and accused the FFC (Forces of Freedom and Change) of being behind it. Then after the war, you said the FFC was with the Janjaweed—and now you're doing the exact same thing again.
Unlikely Target (Low Prominence)	5.5%	لو كنت زول عندك مكانة والا سمعة والا وجودك مؤثر كان قلنا دا سبب اينو صوتك يتفبرك وبي ذكاء اصطناعي لكن أنت ولا شي	If you were someone with status, a reputation, or any real influence, we might've said that's why your voice was faked with AI But you're nothing."

Supply Side: Disinformed by Others

The disinformed by others theory (supply side) argues that the problem stems from the production and the rising number of disinformation materials; applying it to the context of AI deepfakes, we can infer that the problem is attributed to the emerging use and volume of AI deepfakes in the Sudanese virtual propaganda. The supply side of AI deepfakes can be thought of in terms of the production of AI deepfakes to falsify truth (John's tweet) and also the liar dividend or AI deepfake allegations to reject truth (Ardol's tweet). According to this viewpoint, those with corrupt motives mislead the public, who are supposedly objective in their media consumption. This suggests interventions to suppress and control the production of AI deepfakes through laws and content moderation (Schiffrin, 2017; Schiffrin, 2022).

In Sudan, Article 66 of the Criminal Act of 1991 establishes the basis for mis/disinformation by criminalizing the spread of false information. Article 7 in the cybercrime law builds on this and criminalizes online disinformation with intent to "cause fear or panic to the public," or "threaten public peace or tranquility," or "diminish the prestige of the state" with four years of prison or flogging, or both (Knight & Alsedeg, 2023). These laws, while having the potential to address AI deepfakes, require amendments to establish clear enforcement mechanisms.

While social media platforms¹⁶ have made several attempts at content moderation, which can either lead to labeling, algorithmic downranking, delisting, removal, or deplatforming to mitigate disinformation, it is noted that these platforms spend a small magnitude of their safety budgets in global south regions (Helmus, 2022a; [2]). The disparity of safety policy among social media platforms makes it hard to scale and unify supply-side efforts across different platforms, particularly as the X platform has been seen to be less cooperative with Sudanese fact-checkers than Meta and YouTube [1, 2]. Moreover, these platforms lack a comprehensive understanding of the Sudanese timeline and its nuances, which poses a barrier to their independent content moderation [1].

These supply-side interventions, however, require buy-in from governments and social media platforms, which we currently lack. The limited feasibility of the supply side

¹⁶ Platform efforts to combat disinformation often collide with commitments towards freedom of expression (Johansson et al., 2023)

interventions, and the demand-led nature of AI deepfake risk in Sudan motivates us to prioritize demand-side interventions.

Demand Side: Misinformed by Themselves

The motivated-by-themselves (demand side) of disinformation suggests that the problem is not attributed to the rising number of disinformation, as they have always been there, but the problem has to do with consumption patterns that make users more vulnerable to it than ever (Schiffrin, 2017). Extending this to the context of deepfakes, we argue that the consumption patterns of disinformation in general are more concerning than the novelty or the adoption scale of the AI deepfake technology. This is evident by the limited number of AI deepfakes as compared to traditional disinformation in the Sudanese feeds [1]. In our analysis we treat the AI deepfake demand side as being influenced by motivated reasoning, cognitive efforts, and AI literacy, with motivated reasoning especially influential.

Motivated reasoning

Motivated reasoning can manifest in three ways: first, filter bubbles impact exposure to deepfake content. Second, motivated reasoning leading to the perception of authentic footage as deepfake (perceived deepfake). Third, motivated reasoning and narratives impact reaction and interpretation of AI deepfake material (demand side) [2]. The first manifestation is important when looking at deepfakes in the context of social media algorithms, particularly the echo-chamber effect¹⁷, as attention-seeking algorithms expose viewers to identity-confirming content¹⁸, which means their biases not only shape their truth judgement but also what they are exposed to in the first place. The second manifestation deals with what we refer to as a “perceived AI deepfake.” Ardol’s tweet represents a textbook case of the liar dividend, where the deepfake allegation was made to protect the politician’s reputation and thus relates to the liar dividend and the disinformed by others side. This differs slightly from Hmedti’s death, which was viral not only because of the SAF supporters’¹⁹ led propaganda

¹⁷This poses a limitation for our sampling. We discuss the limitations in more detail in Annex B.

¹⁸Improving the transparency of the algorithms would require collaboration from social media platforms, which we currently lack.

¹⁹ It is also often assumed to be Islamist-led propaganda.

but also because segments of the public were inclined to believe it themselves, given their emotional attachment to the context, which makes the motivated reasoning effect clearer in supplying and mobilizing deepfakes and blurs the line between “others” and themselves in causing the disinformation. Thirdly, motivated reasoning can also help us understand the reaction to actual and perceived deepfake content.²⁰ The analysis of comments on John's tweet, a technical AI deepfake footage, revealed a significant theme: motivated reasoning plays a huge role in tweet consumption as compared to footage truthfulness²¹ as seen by the “agree with the media, disagree with narrative/context” theme. Comments on Ardol's tweet also showed how motivated reasoning shaped by previous beliefs—the actor's backing and reputation—might influence reaction towards the alleged deepfake.²² This suggests that while the public mostly appears to be unaffected by the AI-generated deepfakes, this is a misleading sense of safety. In many cases, opposition to AI deepfake deception results from a lack of political alignment rather than AI detection skills. As a result, the public may be vulnerable to deception if future malicious actors deliberately create a realistic AI deepfake scenario and strategic publication campaigns.

The motivated reasoning argument can be extended to the discussion on fact-check interventions to combat AI deepfakes, discussed later; there exists the risk of human fact-checkers and individual civic tech practitioners being biased (Johansson et al., 2023; [2]) or at least perceived to be biased in low-trust media contexts. Bias accusations of fact-checkers are already prevalent in the Sudanese media [1, 2]. This perception may stem from the longstanding lack of trust in the Sudanese media, which has long lacked objectivity. Alternatively, it may reflect the motivated reasoning of users who perceive fact checks to be biased when they do not align with their political views [1].

The political identity model suggests using targeted process-based interventions that are specific to the cognitive bias involved (Van Bavel & Pereira, 2018). It recommends deploying interventions that aim to change the underlying associations or activate alternative social

²⁰ Crowd wisdom also impacts public reaction, as their views might conform to majority opinion.

²¹ This is known as confirmation bias, where people judge claims as more credible when those claims align with their prior beliefs or identities.

²² The “critical analysis/fact inconsistency” might also relate to motivated reasoning. Refer to the limitations in Annex B

identities. Here we discuss psychological interventions that encourage deep engagement with political content.

Pre-bunking. It involves pre-event measures that expose users (demand side) to doses of disinformation in order for them to develop immunity against different manipulation techniques (e.g., inoculation games). These interventions have been shown to generalize across different political ideologies (Roozenbeek & Van Der Linden, 2019; Roozenbeek et al., 2022). An AI deepfake-specific prebunking would include exposing the users to AI-generated content to develop detection skills and get a sense of the AI capabilities while also moderating the influence of political identity. Criticism of inoculation games includes that people were more skeptical and uncertain in general than they were able to distinguish truth from disinformation (Johansson et al., 2023). This calls for their conscious application in the context of Sudan, as it might lead to more AI skepticism.

Cognitive Effort

While acknowledging limitations in our examination of cognitive efforts²³, we consider its influence well-supported by prior research. This view suggests that the public are lazy but objective in their consumption of deepfake content; therefore, interventions equip the public with the right information and encourage them to spend more cognitive effort in consuming content. We classified these interventions based on the time of intervention as pre-event and post-event measures.

Media literacy. A notable pre-event measure is media literacy, which involves educating users about disinformation and equipping them with skills to help them navigate digital spaces. It has proven effective, particularly in the context of breaking news and evaluating partisan views (Johansson et al., 2023). While media literacy efforts can be initiated by several actors, they stem from a user-centric approach that allows the public to better detect disinformation. This matches Beam's²⁴ approach to combating disinformation [1]. Despite concerns over its limited scalability, voluntary adoption, and risk of overconfidence in future

²³ Our analysis relied on comments and lacked CRT scores of the commenters. More details on limitations can be found in Annex B.

²⁴ Beam Reports is a Sudanese fact-checking organization that focuses on empowering the public with fact-checking resources and educational materials to equip them with the necessary skills to navigate the complex media space in Sudan.

truth evaluation (Johansson et al., 2023; [2]), media literacy remains one of the prominent proactive measures that empowers users to detect disinformation. In the context of AI deepfake mitigation, context-sensitive media literacy programs hold the promise of user empowerment, given that specific AI knowledge and toolkits have been integrated into these programs.

In the post-event interventions we discuss fact-checking, tiplines, debunking, and self-help resources.

Fact-checking. The most prominent post-event measure is fact-checking. Although fact-checking is reactive, post-event, and message-based, it has proven to be effective (Ahmed, 2021; Johansson et al., 2023), and unlike general warning interventions, it does not influence perceptions of truthful content. In the context of Sudan, the only organization that is part of Meta’s third-party fact-check program is Beam Reports (Suliman, 2024). The program ensures that their fact-checking efforts translate into “False” labels and correction context on the platform [1].

Despite the potential of fact-checking efforts in combating AI deepfakes in Sudan, they have limitations relative to their scalability, visibility, and effectiveness. The scale problem with fact-checking lies in its dependency on the assessment of human fact-checkers. The limited reach of the fact-checking reports compared to the deepfake content poses the most important barrier for Beam and other Sudanese fact-checking organizations to reach their audience (Staff, 2018; [1, 2]). It is important to consider the digital nature of fact-checking reports, which contributes to their limited accessibility. The real and perceived AI deepfakes spread widely in Sudanese households through both digital and non-digital means; therefore, addressing them through digital means alone ignores how the digital divide complicates the nature of the problem (Oliver, 2021). The lingering impact of deepfakes represents a serious problem, as the public might resist correction and trust the initial communication more than subsequent communication²⁵ due to heuristics, bias, or lack of alternative explanation (Kahan, 2017a; Van Bavel & Pereira, 2018). This is further exacerbated by the visual nature of AI deepfakes. A problem Beam Reports found to be prevailing in their work in combating AI deepfakes is the challenge of visual memory correction [1].

²⁵In the literature, it is known as the “continued influence effect.”

Debunking. Debunking is a post-event intervention that clarifies the falsity of deepfakes by addressing the question of "why they are fake," distinguishing it from fact-checking labels that merely provide a label. Research suggests that debunking is effective because it provides an alternative account in place of the deepfake (Johansson et al., 2023). The effectiveness of debunking depends on its reach and the trust placed in the actor responsible for the debunking. Moreover, there is research contesting the effectiveness of debunking, claiming that it has been shown to be impactful only in cases where participants held low or medium belief but not strong belief in the news (Johansson et al., 2023). This is relevant to the context of deepfakes in Sudan, as interventions must address both believers and skeptics of AI deepfakes. To ensure successful debunking, it is important to address the limited accessibility and reliability of official sources of information, a crucial challenge for Sudanese journalists and fact-checkers [1].

Tiplines and self-help resources. Closed-source environments²⁶ represent a critical dimension to consider when designing AI deepfake interventions. In Sudan, WhatsApp groups are considered incubators of disinformation and AI deepfake propaganda [1]. While it is technically possible to track deepfakes and disinformation in a closed-source environment, there seems to be limited acceptability for its practical application. This makes tiplines²⁷ and self-help resources in WhatsApp very relevant for empowering users in these closed environments. An inspiring initiative was led by WhatsApp in partnership with Brazil's Election Authority (BEA), in which they launched a bot to which users could send messages that they suspected to be fake and receive fact-checks (Johansson et al., 2023). Transferring this initiative to the context of Sudan through partnerships with local fact-checking organizations will ensure public empowerment with fact-checking knowledge, even in closed-source environments. While tiplines can enable accessibility to already existing fact-check databases, they lack scalability beyond the existing fact-check materials.

AI-Assisted Interventions. There have also been attempts to integrate AI in scaling the fact-checks, which results in enriching the self-help resources. AI tools with their wide

²⁶ Closed-source environments are platforms where data is not publicly accessible (e.g., WhatsApp, Signal). Their limited accessibility represents a challenge for fact-checking efforts in these environments.

²⁷ Tiplines are accounts to which users can forward messages that they suspect to include false content, and as a result, they will be connected with fact-checking tools and organizations.

accessibility decentralize interventions and amplify user empowerment²⁸. Notably, there have been some attempts by the public in Sudan to use AI tools to detect AI-generated content or at least understand their current capabilities. In the comment analysis of Ardol's tweet, we found²⁹ that people used AI to gain a benchmark of AI model capability in generating content. The same pattern was seen in one of the comments on [Mohamed Suliman's tweet](#) in which he questioned the authenticity of an image that depicted a plane landing in Nyala's airport, and one of his followers asked Grok (X AI bot) to detect AI usage [2]. While research suggests that current Large Language Models (LLMs) are still not ready to detect deepfakes (Tariq et al., 2025), AI can provide new opportunities for tiplines and self-help interventions. In fact, efforts have already been made to train fact-checking AI models based on fact-check data on textual news with relatively high accuracy. Introducing AI detection and vision capabilities to AI fact-checking bots or current LLMs will represent significant progress in scaling fact-checking efforts and redirecting AI towards serving the truth.

AI Literacy

While disinformation literature provides useful generalizable interventions, it is important to acknowledge the special context of AI deepfakes, as the visual and auditory elements may impact perceptions. This makes deepfake different from the other forms of disinformation. AI detection skills among the public in Sudan are assumed to be limited due to limited exposure and digital access, which may, in turn, lead to overestimation of the AI content generation capabilities [2]. This should be considered when thinking about AI skepticism. In this context, "seeing/hearing is not believing": the visual/auditory evidence is discounted under the assumption that truth can be perfectly simulated by AI or at least assumed to be. However, while this is a plausible theory, our analysis of Ardol tweets showed relatively high AI literacy, as the majority rejected the liar's dividend claims³⁰. Whether the limited AI exposure indicates overestimation of AI capabilities or not, it relates to the evidence on the impact of AI self-efficacy in AI deepfake perception (Liu et al., 2025) discussed earlier.

²⁸ This happens in parallel with democratizing tools for producing AI deepfakes.

²⁹ Refer to the quote in the AI usage category

³⁰ This might be in part due to lack of endorsement rather than genuine AI literacy. The pattern was specific to the case of perceived AI deepfakes.

Accordingly, integrating AI literacy should be prioritized in media literacy programs to build user capacity to detect AI-generated content. Moreover, there is a need to expand the number of AI detection tools that perform well on non-English local languages and ensure their accessibility for local fact-checking organizations.

Between Others and Themselves

This view places itself at the nexus of current debates, acknowledging that people are disinformed by themselves and others, with both the demand and supply side being crucial. In the section below we highlight reputational ranking as an intervention that addresses both sides.

Reputational Ranking

The mechanism is based on transaction cost economics to govern the exchange of information between a network of actors. It allows social media platforms to coordinate the exchange of information while allowing users to safeguard the information environment and promote accountability and trust (Eccles & Dingler, 2021). Given the evidence from experimental research on the effectiveness of the politically balanced crowd trust ranking on distinguishing mainstream from hyperpartisan fake news sources across the political spectrum (Pennycook & Rand, 2019b), we argue that reputational ranking may reduce the influence of filter bubbles on the AI deepfake exposure. Reputational ranking encourages reflective processing (Johansson et al., 2023), which in turn makes users alert to the influence of biases in their perception of content. The producers and mobilizers of deepfakes will be careful with their posts, as their reputation will be at stake, taking into account the active reaction to false labels by the authors of these posts [1]. The potential of reputational ranking stems from the responsibility associated with the act of ranking based on specific metrics, reputation, and truthfulness, as users will supposedly be very intentional in their rating and, most importantly, their sharing, which distinguishes it from the current model of

engagement-based algorithmic amplification³¹. The cost of user experience³² is important to consider for accurate analysis of the feasibility and effectiveness of the intervention.

Recommendations

1. Empower fact-checking organizations with resources, particularly:
 - a. Technical resources: AI detection tools that comprehend the Sudanese dialect, along with other fact-checking tools, will empower them with the technical competencies to navigate the digital space.
 - b. Reach: Increased visibility and accessibility of their efforts not only through digital means but also through non-digital means such as TV channels, radio outlets, and community outreach will ensure that AI deepfake reports reach different societal components (Oliver, 2021).
 - c. Sustainable funds: Direct long-term philanthropic and diverse base funds for fact-checking organizations will help ensure their independence and sufficiency (Oliver, 2021).

These steps are crucial for scaling the impact of existing organizations, but most importantly, for expanding the fact-checking ecosystem in Sudan by encouraging new actors to join.

2. Provide resources for wide-scale media literacy campaigns on AI deepfakes, their potential usage, and toolkits to mitigate their impact. These efforts should target a broad audience through innovative ideas that combine education with accessibility [1, 2]. To ensure that both cognitive and motivated reasoning vulnerabilities are addressed, these media literacy campaigns should be designed to uplevel the AI detection and critical evaluation skills of the public and also help them better address both their conscious and unconscious biases through integrating psychological prebunking interventions.

³¹ Platforms rank posts based on engagement (like/share/comments).

³² If truthfulness ratings are mandatory, user dropout could rise—discouraging platform participation; if ratings are voluntary, meaningful uptake will likely require incentives to motivate sustained effort.

3. Introduce tiplines and self-help resources (e.g., Brazil bot) in closed-source environments through strategic collaboration between WhatsApp and local fact-checking organizations that ensures scalability and ease of access to fact-checking reports.
4. Integrate AI in scaling deepfake detection and media literacy. More research attention should be given to the adoption of AI to design wide-scale interventions. This will require collaboration from social media platforms, fact-checking organizations, and AI research labs, each bringing specific expertise to turn AI into a force for truth.
5. Broader advocacy—including academic institutions, multilateral bodies, media agencies, and civil society—should call for more algorithmic transparency and seek the platform’s commitment to implementing reputational ranking. Such long-term structural reform helps realign platform incentives for accuracy and accountability.

References

- Beam Reports. (2025a, May 19). Artificial Intelligence: A New Chapter in the War of Misinformation in the Sudanese Digital Space. *Beam Reports*. Retrieved August 7, 2025, from <https://en.beamreports.com/21374/>
- Beam Reports. (2025b, February 24). *Al-Athar al-Nafsi li-l-Ma'allimāt al-Mudallalah: "Mawt Ḥumaydī" Namūdhajan* [The psychological impact of disinformation: The "Death of Ḥumaydī" as a case study. *Sudalytica*.
<https://sudalytica.beamreports.com/الأثر-النفسي-للمعلومات-المضللة-موت-ح>
- Byman, D. L., Gao, C., Meserole, C., Subrahmanian, V. S., & FOREIGN POLICY AT BROOKINGS. (2023). *DEEPAKES AND INTERNATIONAL CONFLICT*.
https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/FP_20230105_deepfakes_international_conflict.pdf
- Gambín, Á.F., Yazidi, A., Vasilakos, A. et al. Deepfakes: current and future trends. *Artif Intell Rev* 57, 64 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-023-10679-x>
- Goodman, J., & Hashim, M. (2023, October 5). *AI: Voice cloning tech emerges in Sudan civil war*. *BBC News*. Retrieved August 7, 2025, from
<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-66987869>
- Helmus, T. C. (2022a). Artificial Intelligence, deepfakes, and Disinformation: A primer. In *RAND Corporation eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.7249/pea1043-1>
- Johansson, Pica and Enoch, Florence and Hale, Scott A. and Vidgen, Bertie and Bereskin, Cassidy and Margetts, Helen Zerlina and Bright, Jonathan, How can we combat online misinformation? A systematic overview of current interventions and their efficacy (November 01, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4648332> or
<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4648332>
- Jon Roozenbeek et al. ,Psychological inoculation improves resilience against misinformation on social media.*Sci. Adv.*8,eabo6254(2022).DOI:[10.1126/sciadv.abo6254](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abo6254)
- Kahan, D. M. (2017). Misconceptions, misinformation, and the logic of Identity-Protective Cognition. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2973067>

- Khalafallah, H. (2025, January 14). Beyond the battlefield: Sudan's virtual propaganda warzone. *The Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy*. Retrieved August 7, 2025, from <https://timep.org/2025/01/14/beyond-the-battlefield-sudans-virtual-propaganda-warzone/>
- Knight, T., & Alsedeg, L. (2023). *DEMOCRACY DERAILED: Sudan's precarious information environment, 2019-2022* (I. Robertson & A. Carvin, Eds.). Atlantic Council. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep52679>
- Liu, Q., Wang, L. & Luo, M. When seeing is not believing: self-efficacy and cynicism in the era of intelligent media. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 12, 274 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-04594-5>
- NIST, G. M. (2024). Reducing risks posed by synthetic content, An overview of technical approaches to digital content transparency. <https://doi.org/10.6028/nist.ai.100-4>
- Oliver, L. (2021, September 30). *The fight for facts in the Global South: How four projects are building a new model*. Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism. <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/news/fight-facts-global-south-how-four-projects-are-building-new-model>
- Pennycook, G., & Rand, D. G. (2018). Lazy, not biased: Susceptibility to partisan fake news is better explained by lack of reasoning than by motivated reasoning. *Cognition*, 188, 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2018.06.011>
- Pennycook G, Rand DG. Fighting misinformation on social media using crowdsourced judgments of news source quality. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2019 Feb 12;116(7):2521-2526. doi: [10.1073/pnas.1806781116](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1806781116). Epub 2019 Jan 28. PMID: [30692252](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30692252/); PMCID: [PMC6377495](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PMC6377495/).
- Roozenbeek, J., van der Linden, S. Fake news game confers psychological resistance against online misinformation. *Palgrave Commun* 5, 65 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0279-9>
- Schiffirin, A. (2022). The Pursuit of Truth: Fixes for the spread of online Mis/Disinformation. In *Columbia SIPA Institute of Global Politics*. https://igp.sipa.columbia.edu/sites/igp/files/2023-12/IGP_Anya_Schiffirin_The_Pursuit_of_Truth-Fixes_for_the_Spread_of_Online_Mis_Disinformation.pdf

- Schiffrin, A. (2017, October 26). *How Europe fights fake news*. *Columbia Journalism Review*. Retrieved from <https://www.cjr.org/watchdog/europe-fights-fake-news-facebook-twitter-google.php>
- Schiff, K. J., Schiff, D. S., & Bueno, N. S. (2024). The Liar's Dividend: Can Politicians Claim Misinformation to Evade Accountability? *American Political Science Review*, *119*(1), 71–90. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055423001454>
- Schwartz, O. (2018, November 12). *You thought fake news was bad? Deep fakes are where truth goes to die*. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2018/nov/12/deep-fakes-fake-news-truth>
- Suliman, M. (2024, October 23). *The deepfake is a powerful weapon in the war in Sudan*. *African Arguments*. Retrieved August 7, 2025, from <https://africanarguments.org/2024/10/the-deepfake-is-a-powerful-weapon-in-the-war-in-sudan/>
- Staff, C. (2018b, October 10). *Issue Brief: The 'Demand Side' of the Disinformation Crisis - NATIONAL ENDOWMENT FOR DEMOCRACY*. NATIONAL ENDOWMENT FOR DEMOCRACY. <https://www.ned.org/issue-brief-the-demand-side-of-the-disinformation-crisis/>
- Tariq, S., Nguyen, D., Chamikara, M. a. P., Wu, T., Abuadbba, A., & Moore, K. (2025, June 12). *LLMs are not yet ready for deepfake image detection*. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.10474>
- Vaccari, C., & Chadwick, A. (2020). Deepfakes and Disinformation: Exploring the impact of synthetic political video on deception, uncertainty, and trust in news. *Social Media + Society*, *6*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120903408>
- Van Bavel, J. J., & Pereira, A. (2018, January). *The partisan brain: An identity-based model of political belief [Preprint]*. PsyArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/ak642>

Annex A

No.	Interview Citation	Interviewee Name	Expertise/Role
[1]	(Beam Reports, personal communication, August 26, 2025)	Beam Reports	Fact-checking Organization
[2]	(M. Suliman, personal communication, August 25, 2025)	Mohamed Suliman	Disinformation and AI safety Researcher

Annex B: Limitations

- **Measurement via comments.** Using comments as a proxy for truth judgement is the critical limitation in our investigation. Comments are not specific answers to the prompt “Do you trust these AI deepfake narratives, and why?” Therefore, as event-centered methodologies suggest, comments might reflect partial and irrelevant views. Relating the comments to the themes and truth judgement categories required interpretive coding. To ensure reliability for our coding, we performed three coding passes and documented assumptions in Annex C. Future research might consider developing precise tunnel-based measures for the trust in the AI deepfake disinformation. Moreover, experiments that moderate the influence of individual-level factors (motivated reasoning and cognitive abilities) would be valuable in advancing our understanding of the public reaction.
- **Coding Subjectivity.** In labelling “Critical analysis/fact inconsistency,” it is important to acknowledge that the perception of fact is subjective, or at least it depends on the comment tone. This is an area where the researcher bias might be relevant. We tried to mitigate this by providing a detailed coding framework in Annex C.
- **Platform scope.** Using an open-source environment, particularly X, poses a barrier for the external validity of our findings. Future research may consider working on cross-platform analysis to compare the impact of platform norms and user reactions across platforms.
- **Sampling and algorithmic exposure.** The nature of social media algorithms poses a barrier for our sampling, as the exposure to the AI deepfake tweets might already be influenced by existing biases. Future research might consider employing random sampling for users and manipulating their exposure to AI deepfake content through controlled trials. That said, the generated synthetic media should be controlled so that it is not propagated elsewhere in different contexts.
- **Individual Factors & Networks Excluded** due to limited resources, the research does not analyze the impact of group-level factors and individual-level factors (e.g.,

popularity, political agenda, etc.) on deepfake perception. Future research should consider the impact of these factors and intergroup relationships to examine the influence of profiles and networks on the reaction and exposure.

Annex C: Coding Framework

- We attempted to answer our research question through a between-subject trust/uncertainty measurement for X (formerly Twitter) comments comparing public reaction to four tweets accompanied by AI deepfake footage. The tweets were posted from April 2023 until April 2024, comparing:
 - Confirmed deepfake: [John's tweet](#), [Salah Manaa's 2nd Tweet](#)
 - Perceived deepfake: [Ardol's tweet](#)
 - Authentic: [Salah Manaa's 1st Tweet](#)
- The top 80-100 text-based comments per tweet were extracted, and the sampling was ranked based on the “most liked” comments to create a representative sample.
- Data cleaning excluded nontextual comments.
- To ensure the reliability of the coding, we adopted 3 labeling passes to ensure stabilized codes and documented the rules and notes in this annex.

Trust/uncertainty labeling

- Given the novelty and controversial nature of comments in political contexts, we found that reactions may not be limited to the perceived authenticity of the footage but also extend to the message or narrative presented within the tweet. Therefore, the “Distrusting” label was given to all comments expressing distrust, whether of the footage or the overall narrative.
- The “trusting” category was given to comments that expressed trust in both the media and the narrative or explicitly trusted the narrative without questioning the authenticity of the footage.
- The “irrelevant” category was given to the comments that revealed limited insights into the user's perception of the truthfulness of the footage and the overall tweet.
- The “indifferent” category was given to those who perceived the truth or deepfakery of the footage to be irrelevant.

- We adopted multi-label theme analysis to better understand the comments with the "Distrusting" label.

Rules and assumptions for thematic labelling

1. John's tweet

- For those who distrusted the narrative and either did not explicitly express distrust in the footage or expressed trust in the footage, the label "Believe the media but disagree with the context narrative" was given to them. Other themes accompanied these to justify it.
- The "believe the media but disagree with the context/narrative" theme appeared frequently with the "critical analysis/fact inconsistency" and "support for the subject of the recording" themes. In this setup:
 - The label "Critical analysis/fact inconsistency" was given to comments that either:
 - corrected the statement that al-Burhan is the head of the Islamic Brotherhood,
 - contextualized the specific operation/location discussed.
 - comments that shared RSF violations and the incidents they have witnessed.³³ (e.g., "The Sudanese Armed Forces are fighting the Rapid Support Forces that occupied the homes of citizens. As a Sudanese citizen, the Rapid Support Forces occupied my house.")
 - Comments on the inaccuracy of the translation.
 - "Support for the subject of the recording" was given to:
 - comments that expressed explicit support for the actor.
 - comments expressing opposition for the actor's rivalry.
- The "source distrust" label either regarded him as external party with no knowledge of the context; paid by RSF or UAE; lack fact checks; or viewed the tweet as part Israeli-led propaganda

³³ Refer to the potential limitation of this labelling rule in Annex B.

- Comments with hashtags like "#دیل_لیہو" and "#یل_بس," which were associated with SAF supporters, were preserved and labeled as "Support for the subject of the recording."

2. Ardol's tweet

- The “distrusting” label in this tweet refers to distrust in the tweet, which assumed AI usage. Put differently, the label captured trust in the authenticity of the media and distrust in the AI deepfake narrative.
- Comments with references to statements in the video were labeled as “distrusting,” and their theme was “Others.”
- The “critical analysis/fact inconsistency” label was given to comments that disbelieved AI usage because the recording content matches prior facts.
- Other labels were self-explanatory.